

D4.2 Final report on training materials and events

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D4.2 Final report on training materials and events

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1. Publishable Summary: CLS INFRA Training Schools

Three training schools have been organised, all of which offered supplementary education in fields which the D4.1 Skills Gap Analysis brought to the fore. The first CLS INFRA Training School, held in Prague in June 2022, has addressed the ongoing lack in training in computational methods for textual analysis of the pan-European research community by providing supplementary education in Data and Annotation. The second CLS INFRA training school, held in Madrid in May 2023, has addressed the ongoing lack in training in computational methods for textual analysis by providing supplementary education in information extraction and processing. The third CLS INFRA training school, held in Vienna in June 2024, provided supplementary education in linked data and network analysis.

The Training Schools as outlined by the GA provide a crash course in essential skills needed for textual analysis by early-career researchers and other literary scholars eager to expand their digital skills researchers with a strongly multidisciplinary background, boosting their competencies on the labour market and potentially propelling forward research and knowledge dissemination in their respective home countries. This report documents the organisational process and elaborates on executive decision-making involved in the production and hosting of the training schools and their subsequent training materials.

2. Positionality within Project Aim and Working Objectives

The Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure Project (from now on: 'CLS INFRA') is a four-year project under the European Commission's HORIZON2020 initiative that aims to build a shared resource of high-quality data, tools and knowledge to aid computational approaches to studying literature, build shared and sustainable infrastructure, and widen its base of users.

One of the approaches that CLS INFRA takes to achieving this main objective is the organisation of a series of annual international training schools in the second (Prague 2022), third (Madrid 2023), and fourth (Vienna 2024) year of the project. Work Package 4, which is led by the Huygens Institute for the History and Culture of the Netherlands under the Royal Dutch Academy of Arts and Sciences, is tasked with the executive coordination of these training schools, under

supervision of Karina van Dalen-Oskam. Each year, Work Package 4 brings together a new team to work towards a new training school on a particular topic, with a specific set of teachers. These topics are based on the recommendations made in the D4.1 Skills Gap Analysis deliverable¹, published in February 2022 by Lisanne van Rossum and Artjoms Šeļa.

This report outlines the different strategies adopted in the organisation of the respective training schools, as well as reflections on their practical use and effectiveness. Coordinating a training school is a multifaceted affair; one of inter-cultural team coordination, event planning, and informed and thorough discussion on which subject matter will propel CLS INFRA closer to attaining the goals that it envisioned with regard to its educational value.

Work Package 4 has established the following three working objectives for the CLS INFRA training schools:

- The training schools will equip its participants with new skills for their own research, facilitating the **wider transference of skills** for the computational study of literature;
- The training schools will aim for **inclusivity** to participants from diverse backgrounds (gender, career stage, geographical location, language community, functional ability);
- The training schools will contribute to a growing sense of **interconnectedness** among its practitioner community.

In the following, we will provide a chronological overview of the organisation and reception of the three training schools.

¹ Lisanne M. van Rossum, & Artjoms Šeļa (2022). CLS INFRA D4.1 Skills Gap Analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6421513>

3. Prague Training School 2022: “Data and Annotation”

3.1 Task division

Team member	Role
Salvador Ros	Host CLS INFRA Madrid Training School 2023
Bartlomiej Kunda	Executive representative
Lisanne van Rossum	Chief organiser
Silvie Cinkova	Local organiser, teacher
Maarten Janssen	Teacher
Vaclav Cvrcek	Teacher
Michal Kren	Teacher
Ciara Lynn Murphy	Communications
Justin Tonra	Communications
Vicky Garnett	DARIAH Campus Platform officer
Various	Local facility managing personnel

3.2 Chronological process description

September **2021**

Meeting held to establish date and topic of training school. Data of surrounding conferences compared and Doodle with preselected data sent to project team for ultimate decision.

October **2021**

Several brainstorming meetings held with project team to gather input and ideas for training schools. [DARIAH Campus platform](#) demonstration.

November **2021**

[Project website](#) launched for Prague Training School. Twitter announcements to save the date made with WP2. [Participant sign-up form](#) drafted and fine-tuned with help from Prague team.

December	2021
Sign-ups opened and launched via project website and Twitter channel. Production of communications plan for training schools.	
January	2022
Promotion. Internal meetings to discuss progress in curriculum.	
February	2022
Promotion. Internal meetings to hammer out details, e.g. schedule outside of teaching such as activities, drinks, and team dinner.	
March	2022
Information email compiled and sent to participants. Answering participant questions. Keeping track of participant responses.	
April	2022
Final participant selection (in multiple rounds) and decision made about hybrid teaching. Scheduling visits with CLS INFRA team.	
May	2022
Last preparations; ironing out financial details, catering, finding a location for drinks, producing participant folders, etc.	
June	2022
Training school in session - project team present day in advance to set up and troubleshoot last-minute issues. Post-training school wrap-up activities: gathering of materials for publication on DARIAH Campus Platform , certificates handed out, thank-you emails to participants, participant communication channel established through an open and voluntary Whatsapp group link, evaluations held.	
July	2022
Draft version Training School report produced.	

August **2022**

WP2 editing of Training School footage for DARIAH campus platform. Exploratory meetings to discuss Madrid.

September **2022**

Budget meeting Madrid and Vienna. Drafting of data management plan and migrating and compiling WP4 materials to/in Nextcloud.

October **2022**

Launch DARIAH campus platform through press-release and relevant channels (project website, Twitter). Visit to Madrid and drafting plans.

November/December **2022**

Hand-over of tasks and instruction of CLS INFRA team: Justin Tonra (WP2), Bartłomiej Kunda (WP1), Salvador Ros (Madrid), Vicky Garnett (DARIAH).

3.3 Curriculum

The CLS INFRA Prague Training School 7-9 June 2022 curriculum focused mainly on data and annotation. This decision was based on one of the main outcomes of the D4.1 report that data processing and collection can be the focus of future training, especially topics such as statistical analysis, metadata, classification, mark-up languages, and accessing frameworks to existing collections. All these areas were points of focus for the Prague training school, which focused on XML, TEI, and TEI-TOK, Base and Advanced CQL, Statistics, UD-Pipe, Metadata, Multi-Token Editing, Named Entity Recognition and PML-TQ in separate recorded sessions, next to a series of hands-on sessions. The training school used an existing Shakespeare corpus as practice material, as well as personal corpora brought by participants to ensure that the workshop would practically benefit their work in their own respective project languages. The three-day schedule can be found [here](#).

3.4 Organisational matters

3.4.1. Budget

For the Prague Training School, an amount of 2 000 euros was set apart for organisational costs. Due to the international travel situation being unpredictable due to COVID-19 and the 10 000 euros meant for participant accommodation not being a discernible financial post in the CUNI budget, the project team decided to withhold participant travel funds. This is due to exceptional circumstances and not a desirable solution.

The venue and teachers were provided by CUNI and did therefore not represent any additional costs. Teachers and team members all paid their travel fees from their respective travel budgets. As such, the amount of 2 000 euros was mainly spent on catering and printing materials. Because of different tax regulations around the funding of alcoholic beverages, KNAW funded an additional 500 euros in participant drinks and gifts for staff. The Czech Republic is a relatively affordable destination, which played a major role in financial decision making.

3.4.2. Mode of teaching

Because COVID-19 presented significant challenges in planning and executing this event, a contingency plan was drafted as part of the Prague Training School Communications Plan. The team kept up to date with local guidelines and also made hybrid teaching an explicit part of the sign-up form, and gauged participants for their comfort level again in confirming their sign-ups, where they could indicate their preference for hybrid teaching. Roughly 1,5 months before the event took place and the international situation seemed to stabilize with the coming of the spring season, it was decided to opt for a conservative number of 25 in-room participants, so the necessary spacing out could be implemented in case. An additional 15 participants were selected

to attend remotely. During the sessions a designated Zoom moderator was present, and was able to address issues in the comments or pose questions coming from the digital attendants.

3.4.3. Catering

A buffet was catered in the upstairs hall from the classroom. In this way each participant could serve themselves a meal suited to their dietary requirements. Several hot meals were served as well as salad options and small desserts. Participants could socialize and eat at standing tables, or alternatively eat their meal sitting down. No plastic cups or otherwise reusable tableware was used for sustainability reasons. Tea and coffee with small snacks were scheduled throughout the day at set times. Alternatively, vending machines were present opposite the rooms. If possible, tailor-made plated lunches are recommended to minimize food waste.

3.4.4. Activities

On the first day of the training school (Tuesday 7 June), a visit to an archeological site, a Romanesque Rotunda, was scheduled. The excursion was complimentary and took place right after classes. The activity took about 30 minutes and was intended as an icebreaker between participants, as well as offering a unique opportunity to engage with local culture.

On the second day of the training school (Wednesday 8 June), drinks and small snacks were organized in a local bar to promote participant networking and integration. The activity took place right after class, 3 minutes walking away from the venue. A set number of 3 drinks per person (soft drinks, wine, or beer) was pre-discussed with the establishment and could be pre-paid in full. The EU Commission rules around the funded consumption of alcohol differ per country, and as such, KNAW took responsibility for these costs.

On day three of the training school (Thursday 9 June), a celebratory team dinner took place in a nearby restaurant several hours after the final classes took place so everyone could freshen up after three intensive days of teaching and organizing.

3.5 Communications

3.5.1. Promotion

Broadly, the platforms used for dissemination were personal and professional networks, an announcement made through selected e-mail lists, social media (tweets, retweets, and hashtag #CISInfraTraining) and a web page. This promotion strategy worked well, as the training school garnered over 200 sign-ups which far exceeded the number of 40 registrants that could take part in the training school.

3.5.2. Sign-ups

A sign-up form draft was produced in Microsoft Word and transferred to Google forms after a feedbacking round from the local organiser. In retrospect, the Prague sign up form was quite specified by asking for detailed self-evaluation for each learning area offered in the prospective training school, and their spoken and corpus languages. A shorter and more compact version based on the initial draft could fulfill similar objectives through broader or fewer questions.

Questions spanned a range of three areas, among which 1) demographic information to aid in the selection procedure, 2) learning objective questions which asked the participant to reflect on the applicability of the materials offered for their own work, and 3) practical attendance questions such as preferred mode of attendance.

3.5.3. Informing participants

For the Prague training school, communication with participants was extensive. Because the number of sign-ups far exceeded the training school's capacity, the participants were kept informed about the selection procedure and criteria through e-mail messages and supplementary Twitter posts. The internationally dynamic COVID-19 situation also heightened the importance of structured and consistent communication. Among participant information e-mails were:

- Explanation of selection process and criteria
- Confirmation and rejection e-mails
- Detailed information message
- Individual participant exchanges to aid in arrangements such as visas and participation transcripts
- Final information messages - along with a short message about expected heat wave with the instruction to please bring enough water
- Final thank-you message with certificate added

3.5.4. Evaluation

After the training school, a short evaluation survey through Google Forms was held among participants. An informed consent document was put in place (and is included in our Data Management Plan). Nine participants responded.

Participants reported generally being very satisfied with the mix of activities (9/9), the content of the training school meeting their expectations (8/9), supported the suitability of the material to their learning needs (7/9), appreciated group size (9/9) and would recommend the Training School to others (9/9). One participant specifically remarked about feeling welcome and looked after by the chief organizer, and several mentioned the opportunity to meet and connect with others.

Some hybrid participants remarked that they felt very well supported (6/6) and Zoom moderation was good to excellent (6/6), however there may have been more balance between hybrid and in-

room teaching. Four out of six expressed regret at not being able to be present on-site or within the same time zone.

Recommendations from participants included better wifi on-site, easier access to shared platforms, a communal ‘sandbox’ corpus, and more prepared, structured, slow, and interactive teaching on a more basic level. Especially in training school environments where the teaching team is more eclectic (e.g. not an existing host institution department), it can be beneficial to host teacher’s meetings to align role division and to promote a coherent curriculum. There was also one indication from a participant who would like to receive progressive training building on the materials offered at the Prague Training School.

Participants also described their experience in a series of short video clips which were posted on the CLS INFRA Youtube: [A](#), [B](#). Excerpts or citations from these videos and the survey would make suitable promotion material for a future training school. Moreover, participants also provided brief answers about their own expertise and their desired subjects to learn, which presents useful information for planning future CLS INFRA training schools.

3.6 Participant selection

Because of an overwhelming number of sign-ups, the initial ‘first come, first serve’ strategy had to be shifted. In this new approach, participants were asked to cancel their registration if they had already become aware they would not be able to attend. To the remaining participants, the selection procedure was explained, and the criteria were publicly disseminated to maintain full transparency. The group of participants was sorted into an admitted list, a reserve list, and a rejected list, who all received tailored e-mail messages.

- The admitted participants were required to confirm their interest in the training school through e-mail after being selected and invited. A deadline to confirm their participation was set, and reminders were sent accordingly. Participants were informed that if they would forgo a reaction, their slot would be reallocated to a person on the reserve list.

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- The reserves were informed that they were not among the first selected, but that a spot might open up after the same deadline. If this was the case, they were informed.
- Those rejected were sent an e-mail expressing our regret at not being capable of hosting them at this time, an encouragement to re-apply the following year and to keep following the CLS INFRA project.

The main criterion in selecting participants was a low self-reported skill level, to ensure that the course would benefit them the most on their skill level. Demonstrated initiative was also a criterion, as well as the willingness to attend the training school in person, as the physical event is anchored in WP4's mission as outlined in the Grant Agreement. This is of course a criterion that can be questioned for economic reasons: it remained unclear until the participants were already selected if travel funding could be supplied, and at that point it was considered undesirable to reward those who had indicated having the financial means to travel already. Because 120 out of 200 sign-ups were women, the organizers felt compelled to maintain that original ratio in an attempt to optimally respond to the demands in the field - gender was not a required sign-up question, and it is merely being upheld as a working category in this context. Registrants who indicated coming from a non-Anglophone background were also prioritized, to be able to maximize benefits for less privileged language areas.

Selection for digital attendance was done in a similar manner, however the team realized that female participants were overrepresented after the first selection, which also did not yield enough eligible responses. As such, additional non-female participants were selected to round out the final selection. The number of digital attendants was kept to 15 to provide personalized training, so the number of reserves for digital attendants was kept equally limited.

It must be noted that the replicability of this particular selection method is largely dependent on the detailed information provided through the sign-up form for the Prague training school. In other settings, where more broad information is provided (e.g. 'nationality' rather than 'please list all your spoken languages', or 'rate your proficiency from 1 to 5' rather than devoted scale statements to each skill area of the curriculum), the strategy must shift accordingly. The resulting procedure

will trade the loss of some detail for the added benefit of relative simplicity. It also depends on whether a selection procedure will be necessary at all.

3.7 Training Materials

3.7.1. DARIAH Campus Platform

The [DARIAH Campus Platform](#) is an online hosting environment to facilitate the durable storage and audiovisual presentation of data for research. The Campus Platform provides online learning resources, event recording and a [course registry of Digital Humanities courses](#), among others. The Prague Training School event page was launched on 19 October 2022 and can be found [here](#). In this way, the training materials developed for the three-day event can be revisited by participants and explored by newcomers who want to learn more on the topic of Data and Annotation for Computational Literary Studies. The page offers this material through video recordings of plenary sessions, slides, handouts, and summaries. A recommended future addition is downloadable video transcripts.

3.7.2. Informed consent for all three training schools

Work Package 4 is a central entity in CLS INFRA's gathering, storing, and processing participant information. The T4.1 survey, for example, relied on broad demographic data to analyze demand results. The 4.3 training schools, in turn, are more directly dependent on specified personal information through the use of sign-up forms to select and host participants. As such, informed consent clauses were built into the communication and registration processes. The consent forms have been included in the Data Management Plan.

The training school website explicitly stated that by signing up to the training school, participants would give consent to being included in future training school communications, and consent to being recorded during the event for CLS INFRA communications purposes. E-mail

communication also reinforced that participation entailed permission to be recorded. The registration form repeated this clause along with a GDPR permissions statement, stating that data would only be stored for a minimized period of time. In the case participants would not be comfortable being recorded, a solution would be to provide the participants with a clearly visible sticker, so they could be kept out of frame.

During the training schools, moreover, participants were approached to take part in promotional video interviews, during which it was clearly stated that the material was intended for external dissemination. It must be noted that the use of sign-up and communication platforms available (e-mail, website and Google forms) informed the way that consent was obtained.

2.7.3. Recording procedure

Plenary Zoom sessions were recorded and stored on Nextcloud (this is a setting that the meeting host can make prior to the session), and additional back-up recordings were made. This was necessary because video broadcasting possibilities in Prague were not sufficient to capture and host 3 full days of training material. As such, a GoPro was provided for this purpose by WP1, and installed and operated by Bartłomiej Kunda. The GoPro proved helpful in occasional times of Zoom malfunctioning. The video data was uploaded after each day to safeguard the material and to avoid overloading the equipment.

2.7.4. Gathering of materials

After consulting with Vicky Garnett, the team chose a post-event resource type formally called a 'Captured Event'. This included the following resources, which can be found on Nextcloud [here](#):

- Videos of plenary presentations
- Presentation slides for presentations to accompany videos
- PDFs of any handouts given during the presentations
- Abstracts to summarise the plenaries (c.50-100 words each)

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- Speaker names
- Speaker profile pics (in square format)
- Speaker biographies (c.100 words)
- Names of everyone on event organising team
- Profile pics (square format) for each organising team member
- Any images from the event
- [Metadata](#) about the event.

It is strongly suggested to plan and allocate the compilation of this material in advance per source type and to start the gathering process during the event. The morning after the Prague training school, the team came together to pull together the resources immediately. The Prague teaching team and Vicky Garnett, who worked extensively on preparing the materials for publication, are currently listed as authors to the published material.

2.7.5. Processing materials for publication

The DARIAH campus platform does not currently support Jupyter notebooks and is not able to independently host audiovisual material. To circumvent this, videos were hosted on 'private setting' on Youtube, photos were hosted on Flickr, and summaries and hand-outs were hosted on Zenodo - Jennifer Edmund can help select more suitable survey software for this purpose.

Person hours for DARIAH are limited, therefore video editing was completed by WP2 of the CLS INFRA project. This could be avoided in the future by providing increased editing capacity at the host institution, which will be the case in Madrid. The overall DARIAH campus progress took more time than expected, with launch in October 2022, which set back the original goal of July 2022 by several months. This can be attributed to several events of a personal nature that affected team members, which will not be disclosed within this official report. It is, however, advisory to devote sufficiently realistic time to complete the progress, and to facilitate continuous team communication and task division.

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The final completion was done by Vicky Garnett, who also wrote a press release to supplement CLS INFRA's regular promotion activities, and Eliza Papaki helped with the dissemination of the final product.

4. Madrid Training School 2023: “Digging for Gold: Knowledge extraction from text”

4.1 Task division

Team member	Role
Bartłomiej Kunda	Executive representative
Anna Dijkstra	Chief organiser (from April 2023)
Lisanne van Rossum	Chief organiser (until January 2023)
Salvador Ros	Local organiser, teacher
Maarten Janssen	Teacher
Alejandro Benito-Santos	Teacher
José Manuel Fradejas	Teacher
Joanna Byszuk	Teacher
Artjoms Šeļa	Teacher
Alvaro Perez	Teacher
Javier de la Rosa	Teacher
Sarah Hoover	Communications
Justin Tonra	Communications
Emily Ridge	Communications
Ciara Murphy	Communications (until November 2022)
Vicky Garnett	DARIAH-EU Training and Education Officer / Summer School training outputs coordinator
Various	Local facility managing personnel

4.2 Chronological process description

September

2022

Budget meeting Madrid and Vienna. Drafting of data management plan and migrating and compiling WP4 materials to/in Nextcloud.

October	2022
Visit to Madrid and drafting plans.	
November/December	2022
Handover of tasks and instruction of CLS INFRA team: Justin Tonra (WP2), Bartłomiej Kunda (WP1), Salvador Ros (WP4 / UNED), Vicky Garnett (WP4 / DARIAH-EU).	
December	2022
Website published. Sign-up form participants produced. Exploratory meetings to discuss Vienna.	
January	2023
Sign-ups opened up. First general teachers' meeting was held. Promotion.	
February	2023
Curriculum was confirmed with teachers. Accommodation was arranged. Promotion continued.	
March	2023
Participant selection (sign-up deadline March 1 st); notification of acceptance via email.	
April	2023
Final practical preparations done; finding a dinner location, producing TNA fellowship promotional flyers, checking participants' accessibility issues with the venue, evaluation forms prepared, etc. Responding to participants' questions and resolving any issues that come up in the process.	
May	2023
Training school in session – project team present at least one day in advance to set up and troubleshoot last-minute issues. Post-training school wrap-up activities: gathering of materials for publication on DARIAH-Campus Platform, certificates handed out, facilitating various forms of participant-run communication channels (e.g. WhatsApp, Discord), debrief session for organising members.	

June	2023
Draft version Training School report produced. WP2 editing of Training School footage for DARIAH-Campus.	
August	2023
WP2 editing of Training School footage for DARIAH-Campus.	
September/October	2023
Visit to Vienna and drafting plans.	
December	2023
Website published. Sign-up form participants produced.	

4.3 Curriculum

The CLS INFRA Madrid training school (9-11 May 2023) curriculum focused on information extraction through NLP approaches to literary analysis. This decision was based on one of the main outcomes of the T4.1 report, which was that advanced text analysis was an area of heightened interest for the CLS community. The Madrid Training School was focused around the theme ‘Digging for Gold,’ centring analysis by outlining three steps: extracting knowledge, visualising knowledge, and storing knowledge. These were explored through engagement with SpaCy, NER, POS, reading files, word embeddings, stylometry, visualisation library, and Lindat. The training school used existing corpora as practice material, as well as personal corpora brought by participants to ensure that the workshop would practically benefit their work.

4.4 Organisational matters

4.4.1. Budget

For the Madrid Training School, an amount of 2000 euros was set apart for organisational costs. The venue and teachers were provided by UNED and did therefore not represent any additional costs. It was decided upon not to provide travel funds for participants, as the funds were needed for the teachers’ travels. Another reason for this decision was the aim to maintain financial

consistency between training schools. In total, an amount of 10000 euros was allocated for supporting in-person participants' accommodation. Team members all paid their travel fees out of their respective travel budgets; teachers were paid from their respective travel budgets or with the travel budgets of UNED, as the receiving university. As such, the amount of 2000 euros was mainly spent on catering and printing materials. An additional 1000 euros, provided by a UNED international events fund, were allocated to a dinner with all participants on the second evening. The WP4 budget funded an additional 225 euros in gifts for staff.

4.4.2. Mode of teaching

Because of the high number of submissions (166 in total; for the application and selection processes, see respectively sections 3.5 and 3.6), it was decided to allow all applicants who met the base criteria for participation to participate either online or in-person. After all prospective participants finalising their form of attendance, this selection resulted in 34 in-room participants, and 130 Zoom participants. During the sessions a designated Zoom moderator was present, who was able to address issues in the comments or pose questions coming from the digital attendants.

4.4.3. Catering

The UNED canteen was opened up to participants, who could serve themselves a meal meeting their dietary requirements and provide the canteen staff with their name to be marked off a list of participants. Several hot meals were served as well as salad options and small deserts. Participants could socialise at the various tables in the canteen, and make use of the reusable tableware provided by this catering service. Throughout the day, tea, coffee, and small snacks were provided in-between the sessions.

4.4.4. Activities

On the second day of the training school (Wednesday 10 May), a dinner was organised in a local restaurant to promote participant networking and integration.

4.5 Communications

4.5.1. Promotion

The promotion strategy for the launch of the training school website and sign-ups is detailed in the 4.1 Communications plan. The primary platforms used for dissemination were personal and professional networks, an announcement made through selected e-mail lists, social media (Twitter and Mastodon posts and reposts using the hashtag #CLSinfraTraining), and a web page. This promotion strategy worked well, as the training school garnered over 160 signups which far exceeded the number of 38 registrants that could take part in the training school in-person. For the next training school, it is strongly advised to include the existing e-mailing list of registrants in the methods of outreach, as they have already indicated interest.

4.5.2. Sign-ups

A sign-up form draft was produced in Microsoft Word and transferred to Google Forms after a feedbacking round from the local organiser. The final versions of the questions are listed as column headers in the exported results. Questions spanned a range of three areas, namely 1) demographic information to aid in the selection procedure, 2) learning objective questions which asked the participant to reflect on the applicability of the materials offered for their own work, and 3) practical attendance questions such as preferred mode of attendance. For Vienna, it would be advisable to specify the different levels by which prospective candidates were asked to rate their own experience level better, to increase accuracy and applicability to our specific requirements.

4.5.3. Informing participants

For the Madrid training school, communication with participants was extensive. Because the number of sign-ups far exceeded the training school's capacity, the participants were kept informed about the selection procedure and criteria through e-mail messages and supplementary Twitter posts, which were produced and managed by Sarah Hoover from WP2. Among participant information e-mails were:

- Explanation of selection process and criteria

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- Confirmation and rejection e-mails
- Detailed information message
- Individual participant exchanges to aid in arrangements such as visas and participation transcripts
- Final information messages (differentiated between digital and physical participants)
- Final thank-you message with certificate added (differentiated between digital and physical participants)

4.5.4. Evaluation

After the training school, a short evaluation survey through Google Forms was conducted among participants. An informed consent document was put in place. Thirty participants responded. The following questions were provided. When they were closed, participants could score their satisfaction on a seven-point scale. The remaining questions were open, with one exception, which was multiple choice, including an option where participants could specify a different answer.

- What is your career stage? (open)
- What is your current familiarity with the field of Computational Literary Studies? (closed)
- What knowledge fields describe your background? (e.g. 18th century Polish literature, stylometric analysis, etc.) (open)
- How satisfied are you with the mix of activities at the training school? (closed)
- To what extent did the content level of the training school meet your expectations, and feel suited well to your background knowledge? (closed)
- To what extent did the content types of the training school meet your expectations, and support your learning needs? (closed)
- How satisfied were you with the group size? (closed)
- Did the training school's dates clash with any other conferences, seminars, or similar events in your field that you would have liked to attend? If so, which? (open)

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- To what extent do you feel that the training school has provided you with a solid basis for your future engagement with the field, and application of its computational methods to your own work? (closed)
- How satisfied were you with the Zoom moderation? (optional, closed)
- To what extent did you feel well-supported overall as a Zoom participant? (optional, closed)
- How satisfied were you with the balance between hybrid and in-room teaching? (optional, closed)
- How did you find out about the training school opportunity, and where did you go to find out more information about it? (multiple options provided, as well as an “other” option.)
- Were you satisfied with the social safety? Did you feel respected and safe, both in relation to other participants and organisers? (open)
- Do you have any recommendations for future training schools? (open)
- How strongly would you recommend the training school to others? (closed)
- If you have any other remarks, please share them here. (open)

Participants reported generally being very satisfied with the mix of activities (average 5.7), the content types of the training school meeting their expectations and supporting their learning needs (average 5.5), and the content level meeting their expectations and suiting their background well (average 5.2). They appreciated the group size (average 5.7), found that the training school provided a solid basis for their future engagement with the field (average 5.4), and would recommend the training school to others (average 6.4).

Remote participants remarked generally feeling well-supported as a Zoom participant (average 5.5), and were content with the Zoom moderation (average 5.8). They were also happy with the balance between both sides of the hybrid teaching (average 5.6).

No social safety complaints were expressed in the survey, and clashes between the training school and other events participants might have been interested in were few. If possible, future events may want to be mindful of common grading and examination periods.

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Recommendations from participants address a variety of different organisational aspects. A common issue could be seen in partial dissatisfaction with the sessions on the first day, which were meant to introduce participants to Python, but for some appeared to be difficult to follow and engage with, while for other participants were quite basic. Overall, this led to recommendations with regard to grouping participants by skill level – something which indicates that a more critical eye with regard to remote participant acceptance may be advisable for the Vienna training school, as there was little filtering with regard to these participants on the basis of skill level. A skill level matching the content level, however, was a criterion for in-person participation.

Furthermore, there were many minor recommendations which could possibly be implemented next year: having more female speakers (an imbalance which was made worse by one of the female speakers having to drop out due to personal circumstances), having better access to materials and preparation beforehand, preparing means for networking in advance and having a short introduction round at the start, covering less content per session to prevent running late and pushing into the next session, providing a general overview of the workshops and their overall aims at the start of the school, hosting ask-me-anything sessions at the end of each day, maintaining a larger emphasis on participants' own research and more hands-on sessions, and avoiding small language issues in the Notebooks used in the teaching, where some minor comments were, accidentally, provided only in Spanish.

In addition, participants remarked the potential for our project to foster dialogue between humanity scholars and scholars with a technical background, and bridging between the two to facilitate dialogue and collaboration among these generally quite disparate groups. Furthermore, while the venue itself was thoroughly checked for accessibility, it was located on a hill, which should have been communicated to participants better. Finally, a participant mentioned they would have preferred more focus on applications to qualitative research.

Participants also described their experience in a series of short video clips which were posted on the CLS INFRA YouTube page. Excerpts or citations from these videos and the survey would make suitable promotion material for a future training school. Moreover, participants also provided

brief answers about their own expertise and their desired subjects to learn, which contains useful information for planning future CLS INFRA training schools.

4.6 Participant selection

Because of an overwhelming number of sign-ups, participants were asked to cancel their registration if they had become aware they would not be able to attend. To the remaining participants, the selection procedure was explained, and the criteria were publicly disseminated to maintain full transparency. The group of participants was sorted into an admitted list for physical attendance, a reserve list for physical attendance, an admitted list for Zoom attendance, and a rejected list for those who did not meet the basic requirements of admittance for the training school. All these groups received tailored e-mail messages.

The physically admitted participants were required to confirm their interest in the training school by e-mail after being selected and invited. A deadline to confirm their participation was set, and reminders were sent accordingly. Participants were informed that if they failed to provide a reaction, their slot would be reallocated to a person on the reserve list.

- The reserves were informed that they were not among the first selected for first attendance, but that they were allowed to attend online, and that a spot for physical participation might open up after the same deadline. If this was the case, they were informed.
- The Zoom acceptances were informed that they were selected for online attendance.
- Those rejected were sent an e-mail expressing our regret at not being capable of hosting them at this time, and an encouragement to re-apply the following year and to keep following the CLS INFRA project.

The main selection criteria were made public to applicants on our website to maintain transparency. 38 participants best meeting these requirements were initially selected for physical attendance, with 15 applicants being placed on a reserve list. The selection criteria were the following:

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- Applicants working in or interested in literary studies, computational literary studies, or related fields were given preference.
- Those with a medium experience level were given preference for physical attendance over digital (if they expressed this as a preference).
- Applicants were given preference if their current research areas or interests related most closely to the contents of the training school workshops.

The initial selection of candidates was balanced in order to maintain diversity in a variety of respects. Notable is the inclusion of candidates from the Global South, which is not as strongly reflected in the ultimate list of participants, as this group more often had to decline their offer due to travel constraints, providing reasons with regard to visa or of a financial nature.

Selection for digital attendance was based on discussions of Zoom capacity, resulting in a decision to facilitate participation of all candidates meeting the basic requirements provided by the regulations of the EU. However, for next year, it may be preferable to be more selective of Zoom participants based on their indicated skill level, or provide them with a disclaimer when they fail to meet our recommended level. The basis for this consideration can be found in the evaluation (see section 3.5.4).

4.7 Training Materials

4.7.1. DARIAH Campus Platform

The DARIAH Campus Platform is an online hosting environment to facilitate the durable storage and audiovisual presentation of data for research. The Campus Platform provides online learning resources, event recording, and a course registry of Digital Humanities courses, among other things. Through the Madrid Training School event page, the training materials developed for the three-day event can be revisited by participants and explored by newcomers who want to learn more on the topic of data analysis for Computational Literary Studies. The page will offer this material through video recordings of plenary sessions, slides, handouts, and summaries.

4.7.2. Recording procedure

Plenary Zoom sessions were recorded and stored on Nextcloud (via a setting activated by the meeting host prior to the session), which was facilitated by the recording instruments pre-installed in the room, supported by a local staff member knowledgeable of this technology. To make audience questions audible to Zoom participants, a portable microphone was used.

4.7.2. Gathering of materials

After consulting with Vicky Garnett, the team chose a post-event resource type formally called a 'Captured Event.' This includes the following resources:

- Videos of plenary presentations
- Presentation slides for presentations to accompany videos
- PDFs of any handouts given during the presentations
- Abstracts to summarise the plenaries (c. 50-100 words each)
- Speaker names
- Speaker profile pics (in square format)
- Speaker biographies (c. 100 words)
- Names of everyone on the event organising team
- Profile pics (square format) for each organising team member
- Images of the event
- Metadata about the event

The decision to gather all training materials in advance of this Madrid workshop proved beneficial as it reduced the possibility of losing momentum after the event, as trainers and participants move on to other priorities. The event page for the Madrid edition of the training school is intended to launch at the end of July.

4.7.3. Processing materials for publication

The DARIAH-Campus platform does not currently support Jupyter notebooks and is not able to independently host audiovisual material. To circumvent this, videos were hosted privately on

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YouTube, photos were hosted on Flickr, and summaries and hand-outs were hosted on Zenodo. Initial editing of the videos was done by WP2, after which the materials were handed over to the DARIAH team, who hired an external party for the task of subtitle transcription in order to facilitate accessibility. This transcription caused a slight delay in the overall timeline for launching the Madrid Training School page, but is a valuable addition in order to increase accessibility of the online resources, and so extend the overall outreach of the training school. As such, it contributes to the overall goal of strengthening knowledge distribution in the CLS community, without unnecessarily excluding those of its members who need subtitles to access.

5. Vienna Training School 2024: “ExploreCor: Using Programmable Corpora in Computational Literary Studies”

5.1 Task division

last name	first name(s)	affiliation	role
Beine	Julia Jennifer	Freie Universität Berlin	speaker, tutor
Börner	Ingo	University of Potsdam	speaker, organizer, tutor
Çakir	Dilan Canan	Freie Universität Berlin	tutor
Carloni	Massimiliano	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH), OEAW	speaker, tutor
Charvát	Vera Maria	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH), OEAW	local organizer, tutor
Durčo	Matej	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH), OEAW	speaker, local organizer, tutor
Dijkstra	Anna	Huygens Institute	chief organizer
Fischer	Frank	Freie Universität Berlin	speaker, tutor
Garnett	Vicky	DARIAH-EU & Trinity College Dublin	DARIAH-EU Training and Education Officer / Summer School training outputs coordinator
Giovannini	Luca	University of Potsdam, University of Padova	tutor
Hoover	Sarah	NUI Galway	communications
Illmer	Victor J.	Freie Universität Berlin	tutor
Kunda	Bartłomiej	Institute of Polish Language, Polish Academy of Sciences	executive representative
Milling	Carsten	University of Potsdam	speaker, tutor
Plank	Lukas	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH), OEAW	speaker, tutor
Resch	Stefan	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH), OEAW	tutor
Ridge	Emily	NUI Galway	communications

Rohe	Jonas	Freie Universität Berlin	tutor
Schwindt	Mark	Freie Universität Berlin	tutor
Schöch	Christof	University of Trier	speaker, tutor
Skorinkin	Daniil	University of Potsdam	tutor
Sluyter-Gäthje	Henny	University of Potsdam	tutor
Tonra	Justin	University of Galway	communications
Trilcke	Peer	University of Potsdam	speaker, tutor, organizer
Völk	Christina	Austrian Academy of Sciences (OEAW)	Event management Austrian Academy of Sciences
Wiederänders	Maria	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH), OEAW	video recordings
Woldrich	Anna	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH), OEAW	local organizer, video recordings
Wünsche	Katharina	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH), OEAW	speaker, tutor
Various		Student assistants	local facility personnel

5.2 Chronological process description

Fall of 2022

Initial meetings to discuss the dates, duration, budget, workshop topics and target audience, as well as planning technicalities, the setup of travel grants and possible training materials. Venue (ACDH-CH) booked.

March 2023

Designing a roadmap/timeline for organisation. Collaboration with the CCLS (the conference of the [Journal for Computational Literary Studies](#)) editorial team. Finding tutors, hotels, and discussing teaching formats.

April 2023

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Booking hotel(s) in Vienna, discussing budgeting, goals for the number of participants, collaboration with the CCLS editorial team.

July 2023

Drafting a proposal for topics and associated lecturers, deciding on format (hybrid/on-site), setting up the registration process, along with first promotional steps through building a website and creating posters. Contact with DARIAH-Campus about requirements of training materials.

September 2023

Curriculum was confirmed with lecturers/tutors. Website content added.

October 2023

Promotion in full swing: registration procedure ready, website finalized, schedule mostly set and teaching team largely assembled. First get-together with all instructors and organizers.

November 2023

First announcement on the website of WP2.

December 2023

Publication of the Training school website.

January 2024

Registration opened, promotional activities.

February 2024

Catering arranged. Application closure at the end of February.

March 2024

Participant notification of acceptance emailed. Curriculum finalized. Working out video recordings plans and responsibilities.

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April 2024

Catering booked.

May 2024

Detailed timetable finalized and published. DARIAH-Campus training materials shared with participants. Set up pre-workshop (virtual meeting on Zoom) to help with software installation.

June 2024

Preparatory online session. Training school in session, followed by the [CCLS](#). Project team present at least one day in advance to set up and troubleshoot last-minute issues. Post training school wrap-up activities: gathering of materials for publication on DARIAH-Campus, participant communication channel established through a Discord community link.

July 2024

Preparing video material for DARIAH-Campus.

August 2024

Certificates of attendance distributed and travel reimbursements transferred.

October 2024

Post-processing training materials.

April 2025

Publication of Dariah-Campus Event page.

5.3 Curriculum

The 3rd CLS INFRA Training School “ExploreCor: Using Programmable Corpora in Computational Literary Studies” took place at the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH) at the Austrian Academy of Sciences (OEAW) in Vienna from June 10-12, 2024. It was a three-day academic training school, organized by the University of Potsdam (UP) and the ACDH-CH from the CLS INFRA project. The intensive program focused on “Programmable Corpora” – dynamic collections of literary texts manipulated programmatically. Participants were able to delve into finding, evaluating, and selecting corpora using tools like the [CLSCor catalogue](#) and [DraCor](#). The curriculum spanned from learning how to use Python and Jupyter Notebooks for analysis, querying and retrieving data via APIs to working with Linked Open Data and how to conduct Digital Literary Network Analysis. Addressing the Reproducibility Crisis, the training school introduced [Docker](#) for research encapsulation. Attendees gained practical skills to conduct transparent and replicable research, contributing to the advancement of Computational Literary Studies. The schedule can be found [here](#).

Directly after the CLS INFRA Training School the 3rd Annual Conference of Computational Literary Studies ([CCLS2024](#)) took place from June 13-14, 2024, in Vienna. This was a wonderful opportunity for participants to take part in a conference dedicated to topics in the field of CLS. The [CCLS](#) is the annual conference of the “Journal of Computational Literary Studies ([JCLS](#))”, an international, open access, peer-reviewed online journal dedicated to all aspects of computational approaches to Literary Studies. JCLS responds to the increasing differentiation of sub-fields within the Digital Humanities, an ongoing process in which Computational Literary Studies has already gained considerable maturity and visibility.

5.4 Organisational matters

5.4.1. Budget

Since the Vienna Training School was co-organized by the ACDH-CH and UP, the costs were mainly divided between the two institutions. The ACDH-CH budget covered costs for the venue, catering and offered travel reimbursements up to an amount of 300€/person. The UP budget

covered the accommodation costs for 4 nights in a hotel in Vienna for participants. The team of teachers and tutors consisted of people from both institutions as well as guest teachers from Freie Universität Berlin and University of Trier. Travel and accommodation for teachers and tutors as well as CLS INFRA team members was covered by the individual institutions CLS INFRA travel budget. WP2 covered the costs of printing a roll-up and name-badges as well as providing CLS INFRA branded goodies for all participants.

5.4.2. Mode of teaching

In light of some complexities run into with Zoom teaching in the Madrid training school, it was decided to only provide in-person teaching for the Vienna edition. Introductory sessions into the individual topics were recorded to accompany training materials on DARIAH-Campus. Most of the sessions used a classical frontal introduction into a certain topic, followed by a hands-on session (divided into beginners and advanced learners) accompanied by tutors. Additionally, the UP team introduced activity-based playful learning methods, such as a “speed-dating-session” (“Find your corpus sweetheart”), a card game (quartet) championship (“[Dracor drama quartet](#) championship”) and an open topics session featuring smaller groups deepening the learnt knowledge.

5.4.3. Catering

A variety of vegetarian, vegan and gluten-free food and drink options were made available to participants for lunch. Tea, coffee, and small snacks/sweets were provided during coffee-breaks in the morning and the afternoon. To accommodate special needs, participants were able to use the kitchen facilities of the ACDH-CH. On the final day, drinks and snacks were made available to facilitate a get-together in the courtyard of the ACDH-CH.

5.4.4. Activities

In addition to the get-together on the final day of the training school, the subsequent CCLS2024 offered a chance for the participants to mingle with senior researches in the CLS sector, promoting participant networking and integration.

5.5 Communications

5.5.1. Promotion

The promotion strategy for the launch of the training school website and sign-ups is detailed in the 4.1 Communications plan. The primary platforms used for dissemination were personal and professional networks, an announcement made through various e-mail lists, social media (Twitter and Mastodon posts and reposts using the hashtag #CLSinfraTraining), and a web page. This promotion strategy worked well, as the training school garnered over 100 sign-ups which far exceeded the number of 39 students that could take part in the training school in-person.

5.5.2. Sign-ups

A sign-up form draft was produced in Microsoft Word and transferred to [Pretix](#). Questions spanned a range of three areas, namely 1) demographic information to aid in the selection procedure, 2) learning objective questions which asked the participant to reflect on the applicability of the materials offered for their own work, and 3) practical attendance questions.

5.5.3. Informing participants

For the Vienna training school, communication with participants was extensive. Because the number of sign-ups far exceeded the training school's capacity, the participants were kept informed about the selection procedure and criteria through e-mail messages and supplementary social media posts, which were produced and managed by Sarah Hoover from WP2. Among participant information e-mails were:

- Explanation of selection process
- Confirmation and rejection emails
- Individual feedback for rejected participants who requested further information about their rejection
- Individual participant exchanges to aid in arrangements such as visas
- Travel reimbursement acceptances and information exchanges
- Training school information messages

- Final thank-you message with certificate added

5.5.4. Evaluation

After the training school, a short evaluation survey through was conducted through MailChimp among participants. An informed consent document was put in place. 21 participants responded. There were closed, open, and multiple-choice questions. For the nine closed questions, participants could score their satisfaction on a seven-point scale. There was one multiple-choice question, where participants could specify their answer, and the remaining five questions were completely open.

1. What is your career stage? (open)
2. What is your current familiarity with the field of Computational Literary Studies? (closed)
3. What knowledge fields describe your background? (e.g. 18th century Polish literature, stylometric analysis, etc.) (open)
4. How satisfied are you with the mix of activities at the training school? (closed)
5. To what extent did the content level of the training school meet your expectations, and feel suited well to your background knowledge? (closed)
6. To what extent did the content types of the training school meet your expectations, and support your learning needs? (closed)
7. To what extent do you feel that the training school has provided you with a solid basis for your future engagement with the field, and application of its computational methods to your own work? (closed)
8. How satisfied were you with the group size? (closed)
9. How satisfied were you with the practical information and assistance provided beforehand? (closed)
10. How satisfied were you with the practical organization on-site? (closed)
11. Did the training school's dates clash with any other conferences, seminars, or similar events in your field that you would have liked to attend? If so, which? (open)

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12. How did you find out about the training school opportunity, and where did you go to find out more information about it? (multiple options provided, as well as an “other” option.)
13. Were you satisfied with the social safety? Did you feel respected and safe, both in relation to other participants and organisers? (open)
14. How highly would you recommend the training school to others? (closed)
15. If you have any other remarks, please share them here. (open)

Participants reported generally being very satisfied with the mix of activities (average 5.5 of 7), the content types of the training school meeting their expectations with regard to supporting their learning needs (average 5.2 of 7), and the content level meeting their expectations for suiting their background knowledge adequately (average 5.3 of 7). They appreciated the group size (average 5.0 of 7), found that the training school provided a solid basis for their future engagement with the field (average 5.5 of 7), and would recommend the training school to others (average 6.0 of 7). On a practical note, they were satisfied with the practical information and assistance provided beforehand (5.8 of 7), as well as on-site (6.2 of 7).

Schedule clashes between the training school and other events participants might have been interested in were few, and no conflicts with grading and exam periods were mentioned for this edition of the training school. However, in response to the question of satisfaction with social safety, one participant did indicate occasionally feeling disrespected as a junior researcher, which is something to take into account and be watchful for for any future events. A participant also indicated that the intense schedule was exhausting in light of their autism. Although our application form asked participants to indicate special needs, so we could accommodate them, this specific issue was not known to us beforehand. The downsides of a busy schedule were on our radar from the previous editions, and a lighter schedule should have been discussed more extensively. Furthermore, the suggestion was made to provide the possibility of adding pronouns to the name tags.

Recommendations from participants concerned various domains of the event. The general consensus was that the smaller hands-on sessions were productive, well-organised and enjoyable, whereas the larger sessions sometimes suffered under the large group size, different

levels among these participants, and undifferentiated teaching methods (lectures that did not leave a lot of space for personal practice). This tied in with a larger criticism on the level of pedagogy, where the selection of instructors was discussed: while they were all deemed exceptionally knowledgeable, some teachers were considered much more effective than others, and a large majority of speakers were male, which would have been good to avoid in such a male-dominated field.

Overall, though, the participants were positive about their experiences, and a common recommendation was to suggest holding more training schools. Furthermore, they were positive about the administration and communication side of things. Participants also described their experience in a series of short video clips which were posted on the [CLS INFRA YouTube page](#).

5.6 Participant selection

Because of an overwhelming number of sign-ups (a little over 100 applications), participants were asked to cancel their registration if they had become aware they would not be able to attend. To the remaining participants, the selection procedure was explained. The group of participants was sorted into an admitted list, a reserve list, and a rejected list. All these groups received tailored e-mail messages.

The admitted participants were required to confirm their interest in the training school by e-mail after being selected and invited. A deadline to confirm their participation was set, and reminders were sent accordingly. Participants were informed that if they failed to provide a reaction, their slot would be reallocated to a person on the reserve list.

- The reserves were informed that they were not among the first selected for attendance, but that they would be informed of potential available spots after the deadline given to the accepted participants.
- Those rejected were sent an e-mail expressing our regret at not being capable of hosting them at this time, and an encouragement to keep following the CLS INFRA project. They

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were also invited to request feedback if they desired to know more about why their application was unsuccessful, again in order to maintain transparency.

The main selection criteria were made public to applicants on our website to maintain transparency. 36 participants best meeting these requirements were initially selected for physical attendance, with 20 applicants being placed on a reserve list. The selection criteria were the following:

- Applicants were given preference if their current research areas or interests related most closely to the contents of the training school workshops.
- Applicants working in or interested in literary studies, computational literary studies, or related fields were given preference.
- Participants were generally required to have rudimentary experience in programming with Python.

The initial selection of candidates was balanced in order to maintain diversity in a variety of respects. Notable is the inclusion of candidates from the Global South, which is not as strongly reflected in the ultimate list of participants, as this group more often had to decline their offer due to travel constraints, providing reasons with regard to visa or of a financial nature, in spite of them being given priority for receiving travel bursaries. All accepted participants were eligible to apply for travel reimbursements of up to 300 euros, which we were able to provide to all participants who indicated requiring it.

5.7 Training Materials

5.7.1. DARIAH-Campus Platform

The DARIAH-Campus Platform is an online hosting environment developed to facilitate the durable storage and audiovisual presentation of data for research. The Campus Platform has a dual-purpose, providing both a sustainable hosting platform for learning resources that have not been published elsewhere, and a discovery framework for existing learning resources that have been published on another platform or sustainable website elsewhere. In addition it also offers a

‘captured event’ format to compile all outputs from a training event to enable asynchronous engagement. The CLS INFRA Vienna Training School will also feature as a captured event on DARIAH-Campus, bringing together the training materials developed for the three-day event so that they can be revisited by participants and explored by newcomers who want to learn more on the topic of data analysis for Computational Literary Studies. The captured event will offer this material through video recordings of plenary sessions, slides, handouts, workflows / step-by-step guides and summaries.

5.7.2. Recording procedure

Plenary sessions were recorded and stored on Nextcloud (via a setting activated by the meeting host prior to the session) for later incorporation in the DARIAH-Campus Platform, which was facilitated by video recording equipment provided by the ACDH-CH team.

5.7.3. Collation and publication of materials

It has always been the intention that all training materials resulting from the CLS INFRA project would be published directly onto DARIAH-Campus, either as hosted training resources, or in the case of the training schools, to be published as ‘Captured Events’, as outlined above. In the lead up to each training event, it has been the intention to publish any materials intended for use in class to DARIAH-Campus in advance. Despite pre-planning, this has not transpired. Instead, each training school has taken a different approach and published their materials elsewhere. Through linking to them on the DARIAH-Campus we have managed to offer an centralised overview of all training materials, often in the form of the ‘preparatory notes’ of all events. However, images of speakers, presentation slides, and speaker biographies were collected in advance and presented directly on the DARIAH-Campus.

The DARIAH-Campus platform is not able to independently host audiovisual material. To circumvent this, on the advice of the DARIAH-Campus team, videos were hosted privately on YouTube, photos were hosted on Flickr, and summaries and hand-outs were hosted on Zenodo. The videos were edited by Vicky Garnett, with support from Sarah Hoover who then uploaded them to YouTube. An external party was contracted by CLS INFRA partners Trinity College Dublin

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for the task of subtitle transcription in order to facilitate accessibility. This is a valuable addition in order to increase accessibility of the online resources, ensuring that they take an approach more in line with 'Universal Design for Learning' (UDL) principles, thus extending the overall outreach of the training school and contributing to the overall goal of strengthening knowledge distribution in the CLS community.